

Pyrrole hydrazone-based nanoparticles as MAO-B inhibitors: effect of micelle-assisted delivery

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Abstract

The azomethine compound **Y3** was synthesized via a classical condensation reaction between the corresponding hydrazide and aldehyde, using glacial acetic acid as a catalyst, yielding a pure solid product.

Y3 and its micellar formulation (**Y3_micelles**) showed no statistically significant MAO-A/B inhibitory activity at 1 µg/mL. At 100 µg/mL, both compounds induced low neurotoxicity in isolated rat brain synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes, with **Y3_micelles** exhibiting lower toxicity than **Y3**.

In models of induced neurotoxicity, including 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA), *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH), and iron/ascorbate-induced damage (Fe²⁺/AA), both compounds demonstrated significant neuroprotective and antioxidant effects at 50 µg/mL. **Y3_micelles** showed stronger neuroprotective and antioxidant activity compared with **Y3**.

The results indicate that micellar incorporation enhances the safety and neuroprotective potential of **Y3**.

Keywords

MAO-B, micelle, nanoparticles, pyrrole

Introduction

Hydrazones are compounds containing an imine functional group (>C=N–), formed through a condensation reaction between hydrazides and active carbonyl compounds, and represent an important subclass of Schiff bases in medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry due to their pronounced biological activity (Ali et al. 2020). These compounds exhibit a broad spectrum of pharmacological effects, including anti-inflammatory, analgesic,

antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, antitubercular, and anti-tumor activities, as well as antioxidant and antiparasitic properties (Thota et al. 2018; Ünver et al. 2019; Popiołek 2021; Ribeiro and Correia 2024).

The significance of hydrazones is largely attributed to the presence of the azomethine group, whose electronic structure imparts a dual character to the carbon atom, enabling both electrophilic and nucleophilic behavior, while the nitrogen atoms exhibit predominantly nucleophilic properties (Belskaya et al. 2010; Xavier et al. 2012). In ad-

dition, hydrazone derivatives display amphoteric behavior, act as both proton donors and acceptors, and are capable of forming intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds, which further contribute to their chemical versatility and biological relevance (Balakrishnan and Krishnan 1979).

From a physicochemical perspective, hydrazones generally demonstrate good solubility in common organic solvents, such as ethanol and methanol, as well as relatively high solubility in DMF and DMSO (Desai and Desai 2014). Structural modifications, particularly within heterocyclic frameworks, such as pyrazole-containing systems, play a crucial role in enhancing binding interactions with biological targets, where even minor changes can significantly improve biological activity (Singh et al. 2020; Karrouchi et al. 2018; Faisal et al. 2019). Furthermore, the incorporation of hydrazone moieties into natural metabolites has been shown to enhance their biological properties, thereby expanding opportunities for the development of novel pharmaceutical agents (Alsantali et al. 2022; Verma et al. 2023; Guo et al. 2024; Vashisth and Raghav 2024).

In recent years, particular attention has been directed toward the ability of hydrazone derivatives to modulate metal–protein interactions, inhibit protein aggregation, restore biometal homeostasis, and reduce oxidative stress, highlighting their potential in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases (Hauser-Davis et al. 2015; Cukierman et al. 2018). Given that the central nervous system (CNS) is affected by a wide range of pathological conditions, including brain tumors, Alzheimer's disease, autism spectrum disorders, and multiple sclerosis, the development of effective therapeutic agents remains a major challenge (Di et al. 2012; Heffron 2016; Xiong et al. 2021). The therapeutic efficacy of such compounds is critically dependent on their ability to cross the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and achieve sufficient concentrations in brain tissue.

Transport across the BBB occurs primarily via passive mechanisms, including transcellular diffusion through the phospholipid bilayer of endothelial cells and, to a limited extent, paracellular transport, which is restricted by tight junctions (Pardridge 2005). The efficiency of this process is governed by key physicochemical parameters, such as lipophilicity and molecular weight. Accordingly, the pharmacokinetic properties of hydrazone derivatives, including BBB permeability, are strongly influenced by these factors. *In silico* studies have demonstrated that many hydrazone compounds possess the potential for passive BBB penetration when optimal properties are achieved, such as moderate lipophilicity ($\log P < 5$), low polar surface area ($PSA < 90 \text{ \AA}^2$), and a limited number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, thus identifying them as promising candidates for CNS-targeted therapies (Bartolić et al. 2024).

To further enhance the delivery and pharmacological performance of such compounds, modern pharmaceutical technology has enabled the rational design of nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems tailored to specific therapeutic targets, pharmacokinetic profiles, and routes of administration. These systems improve the stability of hydrazone derivatives by protecting them from

enzymatic and chemical degradation while enabling controlled release (Patra et al. 2018). Moreover, they facilitate enhanced penetration across the BBB by increasing solubility, stability, and cellular permeability, which is particularly advantageous for CNS applications (Alexis et al. 2008; Blanco et al. 2015; Saraiva et al. 2016).

Additionally, nanoparticle-based systems contribute to improved bioavailability by enhancing solubility and absorption across biological membranes (Khan et al. 2019), while controlled-release profiles ensure prolonged therapeutic effects and reduced dosing frequency (Torchilin 2006). The ability to achieve targeted delivery to specific tissues, including tumor sites, further enhances therapeutic efficacy and minimizes adverse effects (Patra et al. 2018). At the same time, reduced nonspecific distribution leads to lower toxicity and improved safety profiles (Khan et al. 2019). These systems also enhance molecular stability and enable efficient transport across biological barriers due to their small size and modifiable surface properties (Saraiva et al. 2016; Patra et al. 2018). Furthermore, their high surface area allows for efficient drug loading and functionalization with targeting ligands, thereby improving selectivity and therapeutic precision (Torchilin 2006).

The aim of the present study was to synthesize a new hydrazone derivative and to improve its solubility by encapsulation into polymeric micelles. Furthermore, a comparative evaluation of the neuroprotective effect of the pure hydrazone and its micellar formulation was performed in *in vitro* models of neurotoxicity.

Materials and methods

Chemistry

All chemicals and reagents used for the synthesis were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The initial hydrazide, which is not commercially available, was synthesized in the laboratory according to a previously reported procedure (Tzankova et al. 2017).

Compound **Y3** was obtained via condensation of 1.5 mmol of the starting carbohydrazide ethyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-(1-hydrazinyl-1-oxo-3-phenylpropan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (**Y**) with 1.5 mmol of isophthalaldehyde (Ünver et al. 2019). The reaction was carried out in 4.5 mL of glacial acetic acid in a 5 mL reaction vial at 100 °C for 7 h under continuous stirring. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using aluminum sheets Silicagel 60 F254 (Merck, Germany), with CHCl_3 /ethanol (10:1) as the mobile phase. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled, and cold water was added to induce complete precipitation of the product. The resulting solid was further purified by recrystallization from a suitable solvent.

The structure of compound **Y3** was elucidated using appropriate spectroscopic techniques. The derived IR spectrum was recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet iS10 FT-IR spectrometer using the ATR technique

(Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The corresponding ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker Spectrospin WM600 spectrometer at 600 MHz, with chemical shifts (δ , ppm) referenced to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. The purity of **Y3** was confirmed by assessment of the corresponding TLC characteristics and melting point determination by the capillary method using a digital melting point apparatus IA 9200 (Electrothermal, UK), and the melting point was not corrected.

The IUPAC name and spectral interpretation of compound **Y3** are presented below.

(E)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(1-(2-(2,3-dimethoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)-1-oxo-3-phenylpropan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl propionate (**Y3**): m.p. 117.1–118.1 °C; IR (iATR): 3150 (NH), 2000–2820 (CH_3 and CH_2), 1680 (COOC_2H_5), 1640 (Amide I), 1520 (Amide II), 1240 (C–O), 830 (*p*-disubstituted C_6H_4), 680, 750 (monosubstituted C_6H_5); ^1H NMR (400 MHz): δ 1.30 (3H, dd, $J = 7.1, 7.1$ Hz), 2.63 (3H, s), 3.31–3.43 (2H, 3.37 (d, $J = 5.8$ Hz), 3.37 (d, $J = 5.8$ Hz)), 4.10–4.25 (2H, 4.17 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz), 4.17 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz)), 5.86 (1H, dd, $J = 5.8, 5.8$ Hz), 6.44 (1H, s), 7.05–7.26 (5H, 7.11 (dddd, $J = 7.8, 1.5, 1.2, 0.5$ Hz), 7.15 (tt, $J = 7.7, 1.5$ Hz), 7.19 (dddd, $J = 7.8, 7.7, 1.9, 0.5$ Hz)), 7.38–7.65 (6H, 7.44 (ddd, $J = 8.4, 1.4, 0.5$ Hz), 7.54 (ddd, $J = 8.4, 1.5, 0.5$ Hz), 7.57 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 7.9, 0.4$ Hz), 7.59 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 1.7, 1.4$ Hz)), 7.97 (1H, ddd, $J = 7.9, 1.8, 1.4$ Hz), 8.11 (1H, s), 8.26 (1H, ddd, $J = 1.8, 1.7, 0.4$ Hz), 9.99 (1H, s). ^{13}C NMR: δ 11.2 (1C, s), 14.3 (1C, s), 35.7 (1C, s), 60.5 (1C, s), 104.9 (1C, s), 107.0 (1C, s), 111.6 (1C, s), 123.0 (1C, s), 124.8 (1C, s), 127.2 (1C, s), 128.2 (2C, s), 128.5–128.7 (3C, 128.6 (s), 128.6 (s)), 129.1 (2C, s), 130.6 (1C, s), 131.8 (2C, s), 133.8 (1C, s), 134.6 (1C, s), 135.0 (1C, s), 136.3 (1C, s), 137.0–137.2 (2C, 137.1 (s), 137.1 (s)), 145.3 (1C, s), 159.4 (1C, s), 162.8 (1C, s), 170.1 (1C, s), 191.1 (1C, s). TLC (*Rf*) = 0.69; yield = 50.4%.

Incorporation of the newly synthesized hydrazone in micelles

The compound **Y3** was encapsulated in mixed Pluronic P123 and Pluronic F127 micelles via the film hydration method. Briefly, 2 mg of the compound was dissolved in 2 mL of dioxane. Separately, 10 mg of each Pluronic was dissolved in 2 mL of the same solvent and mixed with the solution of compound **Y3**. The mixture was left until complete evaporation of the organic solvent and formation of a thin film. Further, the film was redispersed in 2 mL of purified water, and the dispersion was filtered (0.2 μm , Nylon filter). The filter was rinsed with dioxane, and the concentration of the non-loaded compound in the rinsed fraction was determined spectrophotometrically (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) at 275 nm according to a standard curve obtained in the range of 19–75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The encapsulation efficiency (EE) and loading degree (LD) were determined using the following equations:

$$\text{EE}(\%) = \frac{A - B}{A} \times 100,$$

where A is the initial amount of the compound and B is the amount of non-loaded compound.

$$\text{LD}(\text{mg}/\text{mL}) = \frac{A - B}{V},$$

where A is the initial amount of the compound, B is the amount of non-loaded compound, and V is the volume of the micellar dispersion.

Pharmacological evaluations

Animals

Nine male Wistar rats with a body weight of 200–250 g were used. They were housed in plexiglass cages (3 per cage) in a 12/12 light/dark cycle under standard laboratory conditions (ambient temperature 20 °C \pm 2 °C and humidity 72% \pm 4%), with free access to water and standard pelleted rat food 53-3, produced according to ISO 9001:2008. The animals were purchased from the National Breeding Centre, Sofia, Bulgaria. Seven days of acclimatization were allowed before the commencement of the study, and a veterinary physician monitored the health of the animals regularly. The vivarium (certificate of registration of farm № 0072/01.08.2007) was inspected by the Bulgarian Drug Agency to check the husbandry conditions (№A-11-1081/03.11.2011).

All performed procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (Bulgarian Agency for Food Safety with Permission No. 190, approved on 6 February 2020 and valid until 2026). The principles stated in the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes (ETS 123) were strictly followed throughout the experiment. Brains were taken from rats immediately after decapitation and stored on ice until needed.

Sub-cellular in vitro studies

Two types of buffers were used for the isolation of rat brain synaptosomes and mitochondria. Buffer A was 5 mM HEPES and 0.32 M sucrose; Buffer B was 290 mM NaCl, 0.95 mM $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 10 mM KCl, 2.4 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.1 mM NaH_2PO_4 , 44 mM HEPES, and 13 mM D-glucose. For gradient centrifugation, Percoll reagent was used. A stock solution of 90% Percoll was used to prepare 16%, 10%, and 7.5% solutions. All solutions were used as described below.

Immediately after harvesting, synaptosomes, microsomes, and mitochondria were incubated with **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** for 1 h.

To assess the possible neurotoxicity of **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, the subcellular fractions were incubated with 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of the compounds for 1 h. To evaluate their possible neuroprotective and antioxidant activities in different models of neurotoxicity, the subcellular fractions were pre-incubated with 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of the compounds for 30 min and then incubated for 1 h with the neurotoxic agents.

The protein measurement of all subcellular fractions was performed using the method of Lowry et al. (1951).

Rat brain synaptosomes— isolation and incubation

The synaptosomes were prepared from rat brains by multiple subcellular fractionations using a Percoll gradient (Taupin et al. 1994).

Model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity

This *in vitro* model resembles the neurodegenerative processes occurring in Parkinson's disease (PD). Dopamine metabolism and oxidation lead to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive quinones. These processes are catalyzed by the MAO-B enzyme. They induce dopamine neurotoxicity and neurodegeneration (Stokes et al. 2002). The synaptosomes were incubated with 150 μ M 6-OHDA for 1 h.

Synaptosomal viability

After incubation, the synaptosomes were centrifuged three times at 15,000 \times g for 1 min. The MTT test was performed to determine synaptosomal vitality using the method described by Mungarro-Menchaca et al. (2002).

Determination of reduced glutathione (GSH)

The level of GSH was determined by measuring the non-protein SH groups after precipitation of the proteins with trichloroacetic acid (TCA). The presence of thiols in the supernatant was determined using Ellman's reagent. The resulting yellow color was measured spectrophotometrically ($\lambda = 412$ nm) (Robyt et al. 1971).

Rat brain microsomes—preparation

The brain was homogenized in 9 volumes of 0.1 M Tris buffer containing 0.1 mM dithiothreitol, 0.1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, 0.2 mM EDTA, 1.15% KCl, and 20% (v/v) glycerol at pH 7.4. The homogenate was centrifuged twice at 17,000 \times g for 30 min. The supernatants from both centrifugations were combined and centrifuged twice at 100,000 \times g for 1 h. The resulting pellet was frozen in Tris buffer until needed (Ravindranath and Anandath-eerthavarada 1990).

FeSO₄/ascorbic acid-induced lipid peroxidation (LPO)

The LPO was started with a solution of 20 μ M iron sulfate and 0.5 mM ascorbic acid (Mansuy et al. 1986).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) assay

The quantity of the lipid peroxidation product MDA was assessed using the method described by Deby and Goutier (1990).

Rat brain mitochondria— isolation

The mitochondria were prepared by multiple differential fractionation using a Percoll gradient (Sims and Anderson 2008).

tert-Butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress

The mitochondria were incubated with 75 μ M t-BuOOH (Karlsson et al. 2001).

Lipid peroxidation assay

After incubation of the mitochondria, 0.3 mL of 0.2% TBA and 0.25 mL of sulfuric acid (0.05 M) were added to stop the reaction. The tubes were maintained at 100 °C for 30 min. In the next stage, centrifugation of the tubes was carried out at 3500 \times g for 10 min. The total quantity of MDA formed in each sample was measured in the supernatant at 532 nm (Shirani et al. 2019).

Measurement of GSH content

After incubation of the mitochondria, 0.04% DTNB was mixed with the mitochondrial suspensions in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The absorbance of the yellow product was measured at 412 nm (Shirani et al. 2019).

Measurement of MAO-A and MAO-B enzyme activity

The monoamine oxidase activity assay of both recombinant human MAO-A (*hMAOA*) and MAO-B (*hMAOB*) was performed using a fluorometric method with Amplex® UltraRed reagent to detect hydrogen peroxide or peroxidase activity in biological samples or enzymes (Bautista-Aguilera et al. 2014), with small modifications (Kasabova-Angelova et al. 2020). In the presence of peroxidase, Amplex® Red reacted 1:1 stoichiometrically with hydrogen peroxide to produce a red phosphorescent oxidation product, resorufin. Due to the high extinction coefficient (58,000 \pm 5,000 cm⁻¹ M⁻¹), the analysis could be performed fluorometrically or spectrophotometrically. The reaction was used to detect small amounts of hydrogen peroxide (on the order of 10 pM, in a volume of 100 μ L).

As controls, pure MAO-A or MAO-B working solution in reaction buffer, MAO-A or MAO-B working solution containing hydrogen peroxide, and pure reaction buffer were used. First, the substances were applied at a final concentration of 1 μ g/mL. The substances, together with *hMAOA* or *hMAOB*, were instilled into a 96-well plate (eight samples for each substance), after which the plate was placed in an incubator for 30 min (in the dark, at 37 °C). At the end of the incubation period, the reaction was initiated by adding 50 μ L of a mix solution containing solutions of Amplex® Red reagent, horseradish peroxidase (HRP), and tyramine as a substrate for the enzymes, in a reaction buffer, to each well of the 96-well plate. As the reaction was continuous, fluorescence was monitored every 30 min (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 min, respectively) to monitor kinetics in the dark, when the reaction mixture was shaken at a constant temperature of 37 °C. Fluorometric reading was performed on a Synergy 2 Microplate Reader at two different wavelengths ($\lambda = 570$ nm and $\lambda = 690$ nm).

Statistical analysis

The *hMAOA* and *hMAOB* activities were normalized as percentages of the untreated control set as 100%, and the results were expressed as mean values and standard deviation (\pm SD) (GraphPad Prism). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a *post hoc* multiple-comparisons procedure (Dunnett's test) to assess statistical differences in cases of normal distri-

bution. Values of $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$, and $P < 0.001$ were considered statistically significant.

Statistical analysis of the results obtained from brain microsomes, synaptosomes, and mitochondria was performed using the statistical program "MEDCALC." Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM for six experiments. The significance of the data was assessed using the nonparametric Mann-Whitney test. Values of $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$, and $P < 0.001$ were considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of the target hydrazone

Compound **Y3** was synthesized via a classical condensation reaction between the corresponding hydrazone (**Y**) and the target isophthalaldehyde (Ünver et al. 2019). The required amount of aldehyde was calculated stoichiometrically based on the amount of hydrazone used. Immediately after mixing the reactants, glacial acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture as a catalyst (Scheme 1).

The hydrazone **Y** necessary for the synthesis was previously synthesized in the laboratory, following the procedure described by Tzankova et al. (2017).

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme for obtaining the target azomethine compound **Y3**.

Pharmacological evaluations

Assessment of MAO inhibiting properties through hMAOA and hMAOB inhibition assay

The compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, administered alone at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, did not reveal any statistically significant MAO-A/B activity (Fig. 1).

The biological activity of the developed nanoparticles can be interpreted in the context of both the molecular structure of the pyrrole hydrazone and the properties of the micellar carrier. Pyrrole-based hydrazones have previously been identified as promising MAO-B inhibitors, where aromatic substituents and hydrophobic fragments contribute to favorable interactions within the enzyme active site (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2022). The presence of aromatic and hydrophobic moieties in the synthesized compound also promotes its partitioning into the hydrophobic core of polymeric micelles. Similar hydrazone-containing micellar systems have been reported to improve the solu-

Upon completion of the synthesis, compound **Y3** was subjected to comprehensive physicochemical characterization to confirm its structure, purity, and individuality. The corresponding results are presented in the Materials and methods section.

Characterization of the micelles

A clear scientific rationale for comparing a compound in its pure form and in a micellar formulation is related to the possibility of improving the aqueous solubility of the pure hydrazone, which, in turn, could enhance its apparent bioavailability and effective concentration at the site of action (Lavasanifar et al. 2002; Torchilin 2007). Additionally, micellar systems may alter cellular uptake mechanisms by facilitating interactions with biological membranes or promoting endocytic pathways, thereby influencing the compound's pharmacodynamics (Kwon and Kataoka 1995; Cho et al. 2008). Encapsulation within micelles can also provide protection against chemical or enzymatic degradation, resulting in increased stability and potentially prolonged activity through controlled-release profiles (Gaucher et al. 2005). In the present study, a high efficiency of incorporation of the hydrazone into the micelles was obtained (99.8%).

bility, stability, and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble compounds while maintaining their pharmacological activity (Qi et al. 2018). Consequently, the micelle-assisted delivery system may facilitate more efficient transport of the pyrrole hydrazone to the biological target and contribute to the observed MAO-B inhibitory effect.

Effects of the compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** on isolated rat brain synaptosomes

On isolated rat brain synaptosomes, administered alone at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, the compounds **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** revealed low but statistically significant neurotoxic effects on synaptosomal viability and the level of reduced glutathione compared with the control (nontreated synaptosomes). **Y3_micelles** showed lower neurotoxicity than **Y3** (Fig. 2). Compound **Y3** decreased synaptosomal viability by 30% and the GSH level by 25%; **Y3_micelles** decreased synaptosomal viability by 25% and the GSH level by 10%, compared with the control (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Effects of Y3 and Y3_micelles, at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, on MAO-A/B enzyme activity. *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (pure MAOA/B enzyme).

Figure 2. Effects of the compounds Y3 and Y3_micelles, administered alone at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and in combination at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with 6-OHDA (150 μM), on synaptosomal viability and the GSH level. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated synaptosomes). ++ $P < 0.01$ vs. control (6-OHDA).

The first animal model created to resemble Parkinson's disease was the 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) model, which is introduced intracerebrally. This model has been used extensively to induce lesions in the nigrostriatal dopaminergic system of rodents. 6-OHDA does not cross the blood-brain barrier effectively, necessitating its direct injection into the *substantia nigra pars compacta* or *striatum* over 4–6 weeks. Thus, it can mimic the gradual progression of the neurodegenerative process of PD in humans. After its injection, 6-OHDA passes into dopaminergic neurons via the dopamine transporter and enters the cytosol, where it undergoes auto-oxidation, leading to the production of reactive oxygen species and mitochondrial respiratory dysfunction. Because 6-OHDA has a high affinity for the dopamine transporter, it selectively damages dopaminergic neurons by generating ROS. Often, 6-OHDA is administered unilaterally because the lethality of bilateral injection of this compound into the striatum is higher. On the other

hand, under the action of MAO-B, 6-OHDA is metabolized to the reactive metabolite *p*-quinone, which also generates an overproduction of ROS on the one hand and, on the other hand, significantly reduces the level of GSH, the main cellular protector (Xue and Bian 2015).

Administered alone, 6-OHDA, at a concentration of 150 μM , revealed a statistically significant neurotoxic effect by decreasing synaptosomal viability and the GSH level by 50% compared with the control (nontreated synaptosomes) (Fig. 2).

In this model of neurotoxicity, Y3 and Y3_micelles, at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, revealed good statistically significant neuroprotective effects. Y3_micelles showed better neuroprotective effects than Y3. Compound Y3 preserved synaptosomal viability by 50% and the GSH level by 40%, compared with the control (toxic 6-OHDA). Y3_micelles preserved synaptosomal viability by 60% and the GSH level by 70%, compared with the toxic agent (Fig. 2).

Effects of the compound Y3 and Y3_micelles on isolated rat brain mitochondria

On isolated rat brain mitochondria, administered alone at a concentration of 100 µg/mL, the compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** again revealed low but statistically significant neurotoxic effects on MDA production and the level of reduced glutathione compared with the control (nontreated mitochondria). **Y3_micelles** again showed lower neurotoxicity than **Y3**. Compound **Y3** decreased the GSH level by 40% and increased MDA production by 35%, while **Y3_micelles** decreased the GSH level by 30% and increased MDA production by only 15%, compared with the control (Fig. 3).

A suitable model of oxidative stress is the use of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH), which has mitochondrial and microsomal metabolism. Its metabolism to free radical formation proceeds through several steps. In microsomal suspension, in the absence of NADPH, it undergoes a one-electron oxidation to a peroxy radical (reaction 1), whereas in the presence of NADPH, it undergoes a one-electron reduction to an alkoxy radical (reaction 2). In isolated mitochondria and in intact cells, *t*-BuOOH undergoes β-cleavage to a methyl radical (reaction 3).

All these radicals trigger a process of lipid peroxidation and reduce the level of reduced glutathione (O'Donnell and Burkitt 1994).

Administered alone, *t*-BuOOH, at a concentration of 75 µM, revealed a statistically significant neurotoxic effect by decreasing the GSH level by 50% and increasing MDA production by 150%, compared with the control (nontreated mitochondria) (Fig. 3).

In this model of neurotoxicity, **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, at a concentration of 50 µg/mL, revealed good statistically significant neuroprotective and antioxidant effects. **Y3_micelles** again showed stronger neuroprotection than **Y3**. Compound **Y3** preserved the GSH level by 40% and decreased MDA production by 40%, compared with *t*-BuOOH, while **Y3_micelles** preserved the GSH level by 60% and decreased MDA production by 100%, compared with the toxic agent (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Effects of the compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, administered alone at a concentration of 100 µg/mL and in combination at a concentration of 50 µg/mL with *t*-BuOOH (75 µM), on MDA production and the GSH level in isolated rat brain mitochondria. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated mitochondria). ++ $P < 0.01$; +++ $P < 0.001$ vs. control (*t*-BuOOH).

Effects of the compound Y3 and Y3_micelles on isolated rat brain microsomes

On isolated rat brain microsomes, administered alone at a concentration of 100 µg/mL, the compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** again revealed low but statistically significant pro-oxidant effects on the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), compared with the control (nontreated microsomes). **Y3_micelles** showed a lower pro-oxidant effect than **Y3** (Fig. 4). Compound **Y3** increased MDA production by 40%, and **Y3_micelles** increased it by 20%, compared with the control (nontreated microsomes).

A classic model of lipid peroxidation (nonenzymatic) is iron/ascorbate-induced peroxidation. Administered alone, the combination of iron with ascorbic acid increased MDA production by 250%, compared with the control. In

this combination, a Fenton reaction occurs, which leads to increased production of OH• radicals (Fig. 4).

In this model on rat brain microsomes, which are a model of lipid membrane, compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** revealed good statistically significant antioxidant effects. **Y3_micelles** showed a stronger antioxidant effect than **Y3**. **Y3** decreased MDA production by 29%, while **Y3_micelles** decreased it by 43%, compared with the toxic agent (Fig. 4).

The performed experiments revealed that, at 1 µg/mL, compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** showed no significant MAO-A/B inhibitory activity, while at 100 µg/mL, both exhibited low neurotoxicity, with **Y3_micelles** being less toxic. At 50 µg/mL, both forms demonstrated notable neuroprotective and antioxidant effects across multiple neurotoxicity models, with **Y3_micelles** consistently showing superior activity compared with **Y3**.

Figure 4. Effects of the compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, administered alone at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and in combination at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ with Fe/AA, on MDA production in isolated rat brain microsomes. * $P < 0.05$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated microsomes). ++ $P < 0.01$ vs. control (Fe/AA).

Conclusion

The azomethine compound **Y3** was successfully synthesized via a classical condensation reaction between the corresponding hydrazide and aldehyde in the presence of glacial acetic acid as a catalyst. The reaction proceeded efficiently, yielding a pure solid product, which confirms the effectiveness and applicability of the employed synthetic approach.

Compound **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, did not show any statistically significant MAO-A/B enzyme inhibitory activity.

Administered alone, at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, **Y3** and **Y3_micelles** revealed low but statistically significant neurotoxic effects on isolated rat brain subcellular fractions (synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes). **Y3_micelles** showed lower neurotoxicity than **Y3**.

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In different models of neurotoxicity (6-hydroxydopamine in synaptosomes, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide in mitochondria, and iron/ascorbate in microsomes), **Y3** and **Y3_micelles**, at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, revealed good neuroprotective and antioxidant effects, compared with the neurotoxic agents. **Y3_micelles** showed stronger neuroprotection and antioxidant activity than **Y3**.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: The experiments were conducted in accordance with the Ordinance No. 15 on Minimum Requirements for the Protection and Welfare of Experimental Animals (SG No. 17, 2006) and the European Regulation for the Handling of Experimental Animals, and under Permission No. 304, valid until June 28, 2026, issued by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
